

COMPOSITION, MANUFACTURING TECHNOLOGY AND OPERATIONAL PROPERTIES OF RAINCOAT (PLASCHEVAYA) FABRIC

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Abstract: This article presents a scientific analysis of the raw material composition, manufacturing technology, coating types, and operational properties of raincoat (plaschevaya) fabric. Raincoat fabrics are produced from synthetic, natural, and blended fibers and acquire waterproof and windproof properties through polyurethane (PU), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), latex, and membrane coatings. During the study, Oxford, Duspo, Taslan, Twill, Greta, camouflage, and membrane raincoat fabrics were compared, and their mechanical and hygienic characteristics were evaluated. The results showed that membrane and Taslan raincoat fabrics possess the highest operational performance among the analyzed samples.

Keywords: raincoat fabric, membrane, PU coating, PVC coating, Oxford, Duspo, Taslan, waterproofness, air permeability.

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada plashofka (plaschevaya) matosining xomashyo tarkibi, ishlab chiqarish texnologiyasi, qoplama turlari hamda ekspluatatsion xususiyatlari ilmiy asosda tahlil qilindi. Plashofka matolari sintetik, tabiiy va aralash tolalardan tayyorlanib, poliuretan (PU), polivinilxlorid (PVC), lateks va membranali qoplamalar yordamida suv va shamol o'tkazmaslik xususiyatiga ega bo'ladi. Tadqiqot davomida oksford, dyuspo, taslan, twill, greta, kamuflyaj va membranali plashofka turlari solishtirildi hamda ularning mexanik va gigiyenik ko'rsatkichlari baholandi. Natijada membranali va taslan turidagi plashofka matolar yuqori ekspluatatsion ko'rsatkichlarga egaligi aniqlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: plashofka matosi, membrana, PU qoplama, PVC qoplama, oksford, dyuspo, taslan, suv o'tkazmaslik, havo o'tkazuvchanlik.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В статье проведён научный анализ сырьевого состава, технологии производства, видов покрытий и эксплуатационных свойств плащевой ткани. Плащевые ткани изготавливаются из синтетических, натуральных и смесовых волокон и благодаря полиуретановым (PU), поливинилхлоридным (PVC), латексным и мембранным покрытиям обладают водо- и ветронепроницаемыми свойствами. В ходе исследования были сопоставлены ткани оксфорд, дюспо, таслан, твил, грета, камуфляжные и мембранные ткани, а также оценены их механические и гигиенические показатели. Установлено, что мембранные и таслановые ткани обладают наиболее высокими эксплуатационными характеристиками.

Ключевые слова: плащевая ткань, мембрана, PU-покрытие, PVC-покрытие, оксфорд, дюспо, таслан, водонепроницаемость, воздухопроницаемость.

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In recent years, the demand for fabrics that provide protection against water and wind has been steadily increasing in the light industry. This trend is especially evident in the production of children's and sports garments, where materials with high mechanical strength, washing resistance, and moisture protection properties are required. In this context, raincoat fabrics occupy an important position in the modern garment industry.

Raincoat fabrics are mainly produced from synthetic or blended fibers and are treated with special waterproof coatings. Such coatings significantly improve the operational properties of the material. Raincoat fabrics are characterized by high durability, light weight, and reliable protection against atmospheric influences. The purpose of this study is to scientifically analyze the composition, manufacturing technology, and operational properties of raincoat fabrics.

The study is based on the analysis of scientific and technical literature, technical data provided by manufacturing enterprises, and relevant standard documents related to raincoat fabrics. The technical characteristics of rubber-coated, PVC-coated, membrane, Oxford, Duspo, Taslan, Twill, Greta, and camouflage raincoat fabrics were examined using a comparative analytical method.

The following key parameters were analyzed:

fabric density (g/m²),	180-300 g/m²
water resistance,	Very low
air permeability	low
hygroscopicity,	1-3 %
mechanical strength,	high
fabric width	140

General Characteristics of Raincoat Fabric

Raincoat fabric is a textile material treated or coated with special chemical compounds to ensure protection against water and wind. It is produced from:

natural fibers (cotton),

synthetic fibers (capron, nylon, polyester, lavsan), blended fibers. The main functions of raincoat fabric include:

protection from moisture, wind resistance,

mechanical strength,

ensuring lightweight and comfortable garments.

Rubber-coated raincoat fabric.

Produced on the basis of cotton, worsted, or synthetic fabrics. A layer of synthetic rubber or latex solution is applied to the surface followed by vulcanization. It exhibits very high water resistance but low air permeability.

PVC-coated raincoat fabric.

Manufactured mainly from synthetic fibers and coated with polyvinyl chloride. It is completely waterproof and windproof but relatively heavy.

Membrane raincoat fabric.

Consists of two layers: an outer water-repellent layer and an inner membrane layer. It prevents water penetration while allowing water vapor to escape, providing high hygienic comfort.

Jordan fabric.

A synthetic fabric treated with polyurethane. It is characterized by high strength, resistance to ultraviolet radiation, and wind protection.

Twill and Greta fabrics.

Produced from blended cotton and polyester fibers. These fabrics offer good hygienic comfort due to the cotton inner layer and maintain their shape well.

Oxford fabric.

Manufactured from polyester or nylon and coated with polyurethane. It is highly durable but has low air permeability. Duspo fabric.

Based on polyamide fibers. It is dense, retains heat well, and provides effective protection against adverse weather conditions.

Taslan fabric.

A polyamide-based porous fabric characterized by good thermoregulation, resistance to contamination, and fast drying.

Parameter Value

Raw material type Cotton, polyester, nylon

Fabric density 180–300 g/m²

Water permeability Very low

Air permeability Low

Hygroscopicity 1–5 %

Mechanical strength High

Wrinkle resistance High

Static charge accumulation Present

Fabric width 140 cm

Raincoat garments should be washed only in a delicate mode at low temperatures using mild detergents. To maintain water-repellent properties, special impregnating agents are recommended after washing. Minor damages may be repaired using adhesive tape, special glues, or thermal pressing methods.

The results of the study indicate that the operational properties of raincoat fabrics depend directly on their fiber composition and surface treatment technology. Membrane and Taslan fabrics ensure both waterproofness and a certain level of air permeability. In contrast, PVC- and rubber-coated fabrics demonstrate superior waterproofness but lower hygienic comfort due to limited air exchange. Therefore, the selection of raincoat fabric should consider both protective and hygienic requirements depending on the application conditions.

Raincoat fabrics represent an important technological material in modern light industry. They are distinguished by high protective properties, mechanical durability, light weight, and aesthetic appearance. Oxford, Duspo, Taslan, Twill, Greta, membrane, and PU-coated fabrics are adapted for different exploitation conditions. The study shows that membrane and Taslan raincoat fabrics are the most suitable for use in children's and sports outerwear due to their balanced combination of waterproofness and hygienic comfort.

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